

Rebuilding Food & Soil Nutritional Security through Pulse Cultivation

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Kerala has been seriously affected by the recent floods occurred. The topographies have been collapsed and resulted in huge loss of vegetation. The floods have caused huge loss in crops, crop produce, soil nutrients and area of cultivation. The losses caused can't be achieved easily but its impact can be reduced by taking suitable *ad hoc* measures. These problems can be addressed by cultivating pulses as sole or combined crop as they are drought tolerant, hardy, residual moisture using crops, cultivated in almost all types of soil, even on muddy areas, marginal lands with minimum care and having least cultivation cost. Pulses are those legume species whose kernels either whole or split are utilized for consumption by human. Pulses are very good sources of protein and have qualities like low glycemic index, gluten free and even acts as a functional food. It is the best crop of summer fallows of cereals and areas where rain fed agriculture is practiced. Its short duration lifespan fits it into gap between main crops. It is the best answer to rebuild soil health and crop production which disturbs environment the least. They are efficient protein producers from the minimum resources and fixes atmospheric nitrogen efficiently. They efficiently use light, space, residual moisture and available nutrients for their growth and improve the physical (bulk density, porosity and water holding capacity), chemical (pH, organic carbon, cation exchange capacity and biological (microbial population) properties of soil. They offer less competition with other crops due to their height difference, rooting depth, less moisture and nutrient requirement and effectively control the weed growth due to smothering effect. They can be sole cropped, mono cropped, intercropped, sequentially cropped, mixed cropped and relay cropped. The main pulses to be cultivated are cow pea, green gram, black gram and red gram. Pulses have high carbon sequestration capacity, low carbon footprint, atmospheric nitrogen fixing capacity, low water footprint and soil hydrogen fertilization capacity. It improves soil biodiversity as the root exudates attract soil microbes. Since they are easy to cultivate it creates employment opportunities for women. Pulses give a sustainable income to farmer and thus provides economic security. They can be used as animal feed as well as green manure crop. There lies a concrete, promising, sustainable and cost-effective solution in these tiniest seeds. Despite its importance to man, pulses are regarded as 'orphan crops' as it is not cultivated as sole crop by most of the farmers. Attention is required in production and to create awareness to popularize its significance at present. Pulses are good for people, good for soil and good for earth. They tolerate climate change effectively than other crops. Thus, it is beyond doubt that pulses can help us in rebuilding and regaining our soil health making it more productive for the crops to come.

Key words: rebuilding; soil nutrition; floods; crop management; food security